

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Nils B. Weidmann (2019): Mass Mobilization in Autocracies Database (MMAD) (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/FC366E61-6B3E-4B01-9E1B-412249200226>

Abstract

The Mass Mobilization in Autocracies Database (MMAD) is a data collection which tracks political protests in autocratic countries. The data provides a sub-national overview of both anti- and pro regime protests that have taken place in the time period from 2003 to 2019, while covering 70 different autocracies (1). The research team defines a mass mobilization event as follows: “A public gathering of at least 25 people with an expressed political motivation either opposing or supporting a) central, regional, or local government, or b) other non-governmental institution.” (Weidmann/Rød 2019: 1). The MMAD’s data was collected from news reports covering protests, utilizing reports from the following three agencies: Associated Press (AP), Agence France Presse (AFP) and BBC Monitoring. The data is available at both the original level of reports and as a pre-aggregated version of the data at the level of events (1). After the publication of the MMAD, the data was expanded on by an additional dataset, the MMAD Repressive Actors (MMAD-RA) dataset. This dataset contains temporal and geographical data on the actors present at antiregime protest events as well as details on the repressive actions taken, covering the time period from 2003-2012 (4). Of the 30.000+ total event entries in this dataset, there are 15,000+ entries at the level of protests and 8.000+ entries at the level of events listed for the countries of Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia covered by Discuss Data (1). As of summer 2024, it is not clear whether work on the data collection is continuing. The data review contains a link leading to the official MMAD website, as well as two links leading to the download options for both the MMAD and the MMAD-RA dataset respectively.

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Data Review - Mass Mobilization in Autocracies Database

The Mass Mobilization in Autocracies Database (MMAD) is a data collection which tracks political protests in autocratic countries through news reports. The data provides a sub-national overview of both anti- and pro regime protests that have taken place in the time period from 2003 to 2019 (Weidmann/Rød 2019: 1-2), while covering 70 different autocracies (some only for certain time periods) (Weidmann/Rød forthcoming: 51).

The research team defines a mass mobilization event as follows: “*A public gathering of at least 25 people with an expressed political motivation either opposing or supporting a) central, regional, or local government, or b) other non-governmental institution.*” (Weidmann/Rød 2019: 1). While following this definition of a mass mobilization event, the research team also decided that their dataset would not include “*events directed at another state’s government or international and supranational institutions*” (Weidmann/Rød 2019: 2). For a report to be included in the data it would furthermore require information on at least the date and location of the event, as well as have to conform with the above-mentioned definition. Lastly autocracies with populations of less than one million people were also excluded (Weidmann/Rød 2019: 2). The MMAD’s data was collected from news reports covering protests, which were taken from the Lexis-Nexis database, while utilizing only the following three agencies: Associated Press (AP), Agence France Presse (AFP) and BBC Monitoring (Weidmann/Rød 2019: 2). The decision to utilize English sources only and not to consider local language news reports was made because of two major factors: (A) The availability of news in different countries. While some countries may have regular local news coverage others might not, leading to fewer reports simply because there are no sources to report them, which makes comparisons across countries difficult (Weidmann/Rød forthcoming: 39). (B) Language specific skills or software. In large scale projects like the MMAD it would require a lot of resources in order to include multiple different languages, no matter whether the analysis of reports is done by humans or software (Weidmann/Rød forthcoming: 39). Through testing it was discovered that the three sources included in the data collection process alone should cover about 84% of all the events reported in the different regions (Weidmann/Rød forthcoming: 43).

The MMAD used simple keyword searches using the keywords: protest, demonstration, rally, campaign, riot and picket in combination with the respective countries name to find relevant news reports. Seeing as these keywords are however not exclusively politics related, a large sum of irrelevant reports had to be filtered out before coding. Therefore, a machine learning approach was developed to eliminate these irrelevant reports (Weidmann/Rød forthcoming: 44-45). While coding every mention of a political protest in news reports was coded to be its own entry in the database regardless of whether it had been mentioned before by a different source. This allows users to examine possible variations among different reports themselves, for example varying reports on the number of participants (1). The following variables were

included during the coding process: the event date, location, actors, number of participants, issue, side (meaning whether the protest was pro- or anti-government), scope, violence level of participants and the level of official security forces engagement (Weidmann/Rød 2019: 3-8). The data is available at both the original level of reports and as a pre-aggregated version of the data at the level of events for easier use in most types of analysis (1).

After the publication of the MMAD, the data was expanded on by an additional dataset, the MMAD Repressive Actors (MMAD-RA) dataset. This dataset contains temporal and geographical data on the actors present at protest events. It covers the time period from 2003 to 2012 in over 60 autocratic countries and includes information on the actor type categorization, details on the repressive actions taken and the number of injuries and fatalities during every anti-regime protest listed in the MMAD (4).

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Reports	Events
Armenia	723	393
Azerbaijan	797	478
Belarus	1076	508
Georgia	124	36
Kyrgyzstan	1948	925
Kazakhstan	404	238
Russia	6606	3856
Tajikistan	61	46
Turkmenistan	9	9
Ukraine	3415	1614
Uzbekistan	375	146
Total Entries	15538	8249

Sources:

(1) Mass Mobilization in Autocracies Database: The Project. <https://mmadatabase.org/>.

Last accessed 27.09.2024.

- (2) Weidmann, Nils B. and Espen Geelmuyden Rød, The Internet and Political Protest in Autocracies. Chapter 4. Oxford University Press, 2019. <https://mmadatabase.org/about/documentation/>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (3) Weidmann, Nils B. and Espen Geelmuyden Rød. The Internet and Political Protest in Autocracies. Chapter 4. Oxford University Press, forthcoming. <https://mmadatabase.org/about/documentation/>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (4) Mass Mobilization in Autocracies Database: The MMAD Repressive Actors Dataset. <https://mmadatabase.org/mmad-repressive-actors/>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.